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Amedeo Ganciu

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Percezione

Analysis, visualization, perception. Towards a 'sensory' understanding of the landscape

**Greta Montanari, Andrea Giordano, Gianmario Guidarelli,
Federica Maietti, Elena Svalduz**

The paper is focused on some initial outcomes arising from the interdisciplinary iNEST project (Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation Ecosystem), aimed at applying different documentation strategies in order to also highlight relations between human beings and their surroundings, by examining the impact of nature and built environments on emotions, behaviours, lifestyles, and health.

This section of the research is focused on one of the case studies selected under the project, and follows the need to represent not only a physical space but also a 'perceived' one, analysing the historical dynamics between the natural and artificial environments. The applied research methodology is integrated, overlapping digital and traditional research methods, starting from historical maps as a first step of urban and landscape understanding, to enable in-depth research and the prefiguration of strategies for regeneration, and to develop new landscape visualizations.

Changes over time are analysed considering specific environmental traces, such as orientations, urban settings, grids and axes layout, boundaries, waterways, paths, and historical landmarks linked to the concept of well-being and as key elements for regeneration actions.

The research is oriented to frame a data interpretation methodology, focusing on landscape meanings, heritage significances and emotions that can arise from the perception of the natural and artificial environment.

Landscape Perception
Cultural Heritage
Natural Environments
Integrated Documentations
Cultural Landscapes

Introduction

Among different possible definitions of ‘cultural landscapes’, the one related to communities with powerful beliefs and artistic and traditional customs, where the interactions between humans and their environment lead to the preservation of the traces from the past, is particularly significant. This concept is related to the physical and perceived space, and to historic architectures and natural features as essential elements in generating the health and psychophysical well-being of individuals.

The research outlined in this paper is part of the iNEST project (Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation Ecosystem), aimed at extending the beneficial effects of digitalization (Montanari et al., 2023) to the key specialization areas of ‘Nord-Est’ Italy (Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Veneto and the Autonomous Province of Trento e Bolzano). Among the main interdisciplinary topics under development, a specific section is focused on the analysis of relations between human beings and their surroundings and examine the impact of nature and built environments on emotions, behaviours, lifestyles, and health, by analysing the historical dynamics between the natural and artificial environments.

The research of the ICEA Department (Department of Civil, Environmental and Architectural Engineering, University of Padua) is placed within Research Topic 3.1 (RT3.1), titled *The interaction between individuals and their environment*, focuses on the spatial analysis of one of the case studies chosen by the working group: Piazzola sul Brenta, in the north-eastern region of Veneto. The research aims to analyse whether if living in a place surrounded by valuable historic architecture and natural elements is fundamental in generating the health and psychophysical well-being of individuals.

Given the interdisciplinarity of the topic and the need to represent not only a physical space but also a ‘perceived’ one, it was decided to adopt a combining research method, overlapping digital and traditional research methods, developing a strategic visualization of space, focusing on the analysis of the relationships and ‘dynamics’ between natural and built historical spaces starting from historical maps as a first step of urban and landscape analysis, to enable in-depth research and the prefiguration of strategies for regeneration. Historical maps are crucial for evaluating the built and natural environments from a spatial-temporal

perspective, as well as for studying changes over time, in addition to 3D technologies for data capture at the landscape and territorial scale (Farella et al., 2021). This approach to studying the landscape is a useful tool for comprehending the historical dynamics between the natural and artificial environments. It also aids in understanding how human actions have impacted the landscape and how mistakes or problems resulting from past experiences can be addressed to positively influence it in the future.

One of the main issues in this spatial analysis is understanding and analysing space generated from historical architecture, contemporary urban places and green places as a whole space, in which the individual finds himself every day. Therefore, analysing the landscape and its changes in history is of great importance, especially knowing that North-East Italy is a fragile and unique territory, in which landscape constant care and maintenance are necessary to prevent environmental risks.

In the Veneto region the landscape has a range of features proper of "cultural landscape" (Pegoraro, 2014). This terminology is used by the Committee of the World Heritage Convention to identify "a diversity of manifestations of the interaction between humankind and its natural environment" (UNESCO, s.d.). The term "cultural landscape" describes specific methods of sustainable land use, taking into account the characteristics and limitations of the environment in which it resides, and a special spiritual relationship with nature. This concept of a landscape representing the intimate link between people and their natural environment describes the landscape as a canvas on which it has been drawn throughout history and from which it is now possible to understand and recognize past dynamics, the evolution of human society and the settlement over time, "opportunities presented by their natural environment and of successive social, economic and cultural forces" (UNESCO, s.d.).

In this regard, the Brenta River, very important in the case of the selected study, is part of this country and is immersed in what R. Salerno (2019b) calls a "new landscape". This kind of landscape has been characterized since its appearance by a series of artificial and hydraulic structures and very special buildings (canals, embankments, paths between small farms, swing bridges, reservoirs, water pumps) that ensure "safeguard both a stable emergence and a civilized life" (Salerno, 2019a, p. 5).

The reclamation territory of Veneto is therefore an interesting case study, a result of past historical events which nowadays can still be visible in the region geometries of land, water and plantations, surrounded by 'minor' architectures made of rural houses, farms and villas (Baldo, 2015) which are in perfect interaction of the landscape. The characteristic relationship between natural, anthropic and cultural changes makes this case study interesting and complex to understand, in a palimpsest of information that testimony the deep correlation between humans and their environment.

The research framework

The research focused on the relationship between people and historic buildings located in the case study area and if actually living in a small city, with an important built historical context, is a determining factor for the psychophysical well-being of people, linking this concept to that of belonging to a place. Place identity has been considered as the way in which a place contributes to the identity of a person or people (Proshansky et al., 1983) and the composites of its characteristic features (Relph, 1976) and in an urban environment, identity is defined to a greater or lesser extent by the elements and activities of the environment or by events that take place within such an environment, research claims (Cheshmehzangi et al., 2012).

The identity of a place with a rich historical context has surely a great influence on man and it should not be underestimated: it is known that places play a vital role in developing and maintaining self-identity and the group identity of the people (Davenport et al., 2005) and for this reason, it can be considered a related factor from which psychophysical well-being of the citizen can be derived.

Overall, a location possessing a distinct historical identity undeniably influences its inhabitants. As emphasized by Steadman (2003), physical attributes and conditions play a crucial role in shaping the essence of a place and the meanings associated with it, primarily derived from its environmental characteristics. In his article *Is It Really Just a Social Construction? The contribution of the physical environment to the sense of place*, Steadman further highlights that the physical features exert an impact on the symbolic interpretations attributed to the landscape. Therefore, the

absence of the physical characteristics and identity of a location would affect how people perceive and feel about those places (Ujang et al., 2015). This underscores the profound link between the psychological sense of place in individuals and the tangible characteristics of the physical space. In this specific field, where space is not only a physical one but also the perception that the person crossing it has, place attachment is a central topic. This concept is closely linked to the affective aspects of environmental meaning (Altman et al., 1992) and as Hidalgo and Hernandez write it refers to the development of "an affective bond or link between people or individuals and specific places" (Hidalgo & Hernandez, 2001, p. 274) and it is a concept expressed through the interplay of affects and emotions, knowledge and beliefs, behaviors and actions (Proshansky, 1983), developing when "a place is well-identified and felt significant by the users and able to provide condition to fulfil their functional needs and supports their behavioral goals better than a known alternative" (Williams et al., 1995, p. 2, 3). As described in the research of Ujang and Zakariya, in the context of place regeneration some factors are a source of fundamental knowledge for understanding a place and the relationship that the individual has with it and the sense of belonging that it causes; these factors are summarized as the degree of attraction, the frequency of visits, the level of familiarity, being indicated as indicators of attachment to the place, revealing the need "to consider the users' feelings and reactions towards the attributes and characteristics of an urban place" (Ujang et al., 2015, , p. 712), locating place attachment within the psychological (emotion and feeling) and the functional (dependence) domain of environmental experience (Ujang et al., 2015).

In *Image of the city* (Lynch, 1964), Kevin Lynch analyzes the perception of urban space and discusses how people perceive and memorize the structure of the city, including physical and conceptual boundaries. According to this study, how individuals perceive and memorize the urban structure is composed through five key elements, known as 'image elements': paths, edges, neighborhoods, nodes and landmarks. All these elements help the individual to orient himself within the urban space and to find a sense of balance and well-being linked to what Lynch calls "imageability". It would be a characteristic or quality that gives a physical object a high probability of evoking a vigorous image in every observer. In fact, the visual character of a city can orient or disorient those who pass through it.

The sense of orientation is closely linked to the sense of well-being, resulting from a process of identifying routes and recognizing places, resulting from a clear and legible image of what is around us. A physical reality capable of producing images of such clarity, equipped with its own "imageability", also has a social value, contributing to the formation of the individual and the creation of "symbols and collective memories of group communication" (Lynch, 1964, pag. 26).

If we tried to think of being lost, with no idea where we are, our balance would be undermined and a sense of confusion and anxiety would immediately come over us. Staying in environments that are intuitive, welcoming and that facilitate easy orientation for those who use them, not only makes places more human and sustainable, where people feel connected to the surrounding environment (Alexander, 1977) but is also a cause of connection between people. If it is true, as Lynch says, that a vivid and integrated landscape is "the skeleton on which primitive peoples build socially important myths", then these common memories linked to the same place will be a point of contact between individuals. "A good environmental image gives its owner an important sense of emotional security. It allows him to establish a harmonious relationship between himself and the surrounding world. This constitutes a feeling, as opposed to the bewilderment of those who have lost their orientation: the sweet feeling of one's home is stronger when the home is not only familiar, but also distinctive" (Lynch, 1964, p. 26) The clarity of legibility of a place therefore also largely influences people's emotional security, making them comfortable and in communication with the natural environment around them, the built environment and other people.

Research actions and achieved results

Considering the case study of Piazzola sul Brenta, a small municipality in the Veneto region, a territorial analysis was carried out, with the aim to understand the dynamics existing between the natural and artificial environments. In this specific field, where space is not only a physical one but also the perception that the person crossing has, the interdisciplinary approach is of underlying importance. Therefore, the first part of the spatial analysis focused on the comparison of the state of the art for the

Fig. 1 Methodology scheme used to study the historically stratified State of Art.

case study under analysis with historical maps. This approach to landscape analysis provides invaluable assistance in comprehending the historical interactions between the built and natural environments, but it also aids in comprehending how human behaviour had a favourable impact on the landscape and how it might be in the future, resolving mistakes or issues resulted from past experiences.

The initial phase of the investigation involved a thorough examination of historical maps to gain insights into the evolution of both the constructed and natural environments. The primary emphasis during this initial analysis was placed on scrutinizing the historical transformations of the Brenta riverbed and Villa Came-rini-Contarini.

The research started by examining historical maps sourced from the State Archive of Venice, specifically those illustrating the Villa and depicting the interplay between the Villa and the course of the Brenta River. By closely examining primarily two maps and overlaying them onto the present-day landscape, notable shifts in the curvature of the Brenta River become evident. The analysis reveals a deliberate alteration in the river's course, characterized by the construction of a deviation designed to facilitate field irrigation.

Analysing the anthropic spaces within the territorial borders of Piazzola sul Brenta, previously developed studies revealed the presence of Roman axes crossing the village, albeit eventually fading away. Furthermore, an examination of Piazzola's urban grid was conducted, and a comparison with the orientation of the Roman axes was undertaken. However, no alignment was observed

between them. This preliminary analysis has brought to light the historical significance of Villa Contarini. Specifically, it became clear that the village's urban layout has diverged from the Roman axes and, instead, aligns with the grid influenced by the orientation of Villa Contarini.

From this analysis of historical maps it was possible to understand how natural landscape had changed and if it had changed due to human actions. Through the use of historical maps and their analysis as a 'palimpsest', the research traced the history of the natural feature defining this small urban setting – the Brenta River – and the architectural element that significantly shapes the place's identity. Particularly, this analysis underscored the profound impact of Villa Contarini on Piazzola, revealing that the entire urban layout is structured around the orientation of the Villa. This departure from the ancient Roman axes highlights the considerable influence of Villa Contarini on shaping the town's spatial organization.

During this comparison between historical maps and the State of Art, a crucial question arose regarding the borders. Since Piazzola sul Brenta is a small urban reality, immersed in the Venetian countryside, the boundary between the city and the countryside is not clear. Indeed, the buildings gradually thin out, intersecting with the geometries of the landscape and supporting its shapes, but when does the city end and the countryside begin? This topic is certainly of great importance in a research focusing on the interaction between human beings, environment and nature. Indeed, borders can be natural or artificial, but they can also be 'perceived' borders. In his work *The Image of the City* Kevin Lynch examines the way individuals perceive urban spaces. He delves into the processes through which people form impressions and memories of a city's structure, encompassing both its physical and conceptual boundaries. A central topic of his analysis is the concept of "border perception" and the role that borders play in creating coherent and understandable mental images of the city. As outlined in this research, individuals construct their perception and memory of urban structure through five fundamental components referred to as "image elements." These elements, namely paths, edges, neighbourhoods, nodes, and landmarks, collectively shape the cognitive map of the city. Specifically, the concept of 'edges' plays a crucial role in how boundaries are perceived in this cognitive mapping process.

Therefore, recognizable and clear boundaries influence the orientation that the individual has of the city, avoiding a sense of loss which would interfere with the perception that inhabitants have of the space. "Although clarity and legibility are not the only important properties in a beautiful city," Lynch points out, "it acquires special importance if the environment is examined in the urban dimensions of extent, time and complexity. To understand this, we must consider the city not as an object in itself, but in the ways in which it is perceived by its inhabitants" (Lynch, 1964, p. 25). Losing orientation causes a sense of confusion which undermines the citizen's sense of well-being and balance, a balance towards which all individuals unconsciously tend "in all moments of their physical and mental existence" (Arnheim, 1962, p. 50). The perception of these limits, whether material or immaterial, leads to the construction of a cohesive mental image of the city which influences people's ability to orient themselves and interact with the space around them, translating this image into behaviors and habits that citizens take on in everyday urban space (Lynch, 1964).

If we consider a clear natural limit in Piazzola sul Brenta it is certainly the Brenta river. Deeply linked to the history of the city, so much so as to be part of its very name, the relationships between citizens and this waterway were innumerable in the past. The course of the river (fig. 1) was diverted to irrigate the fields, probably through the 'Roggia Contarina', to bring water to the mills, but also to fill the artificial lake and the moat of Villa Contarini, in which impressive naumachias were staged. In the late nineteenth century the river water was used by jute factories, becoming a fundamental element for the industrial period of Piazzola sul Brenta, as it can be seen through landscape geometry.

Considering the border of the municipality of Piazzola sul Brenta (fig. 2), it can be easily noticed that the riverbed coincides with the administrative limit of the municipality: covering an area of approximately 41 km², the municipality border skirts the Brenta river to the east, reaching the locality of Carturo to the north and Vaccarino to the south.

The coincidence of the Carturo Bridge and the extreme north of the administrative limit of the municipality confirms the close link between the administrative border and the one related to the landscape: the natural element of the river and the artificial one of the bridge. We can therefore say that the administrative border interacts with the natural space.

Fig. 2. Piazzola sul Brenta. Routes of the waterways draw borders on the landscape.

Fig. 3. The municipality border coincides with the surrounding landscape.

At the contrary, looking at the administrative border of the city it appears that it does not communicate with the environment around it. The border indeed follows a geometry purely linked to the built, artificial space, detaching itself from the natural designs of the landscape. For example, within the border Villa Contarini Camerini is considered but its park, a very important element of the urban space, is not included. Even the border that delimits the eastern area refers only to buildings, overshadowing what is one of the strongest limits in the area: the Brenta River. Looking at the following images (fig. 3) which compare the municipal and city administrative limits, albeit at different scales, it can be noticed the diversity of the line graphics and how

these signs fit in with the surrounding landscape (municipal limit) or in complete disagreement (city limit), union of segmented lines.

Since this research aims to study the interaction between man, the natural environment and the built environment, it was decided to create an imaginary limit, which corresponds to the interaction between artificial and natural elements. Just over a kilometre from Villa Contarini Camerini, the river delimits the city to the east, with a sinuous but clear geometry, interacting with the city centre thanks to artificial canals dug in the past and above all via Roggia Contarina, a direct connection with the river.

Due to its strong historical and environmental value, we will consider the Brenta river as the eastern border of Piazzola sul Brenta, then following the geometry of Roggia Contarina to close the north-east border and include the park of the Villa within this hypothetical spatial border.

If it is true that clear limits can simplify urban reading (Lynch, 1964), then in the study of understanding the perception and cognition of space, orientation is a key element in the regenerative nature of a place and in influencing the well-being of the people who live this space. Kevin Lynch associates the concept of orientation with the sense of belonging to a place, in fact the importance of sensory perception, including that linked to orientation, is fundamental in shaping our connection with spaces (Pallasmaa, 2005).

Juhani Pallasmaa (2005) underlines the importance of the sensorial experience of architecture, as of a work of art, which manages to stimulate all our senses, not just the visual one:

Architectural theorising, education and practices have primarily been concerned with form. Yet, we have an astonishing capacity to perceive and grasp unconsciously and

Fig. 4. The municipality border in relation with the landscape (on the left). The administrative city border of Piazzola sul Brenta doesn't dialogue with the natural space (on the right).

peripherally complex environmental entities and atmospheres. Atmospheric characteristics of spaces, places and settings are grasped before any conscious observation of details is made. (Pallasmaa 2005, p. 7)

The significance of a place identity steeped in a profound historical background should not be overlooked. It is widely acknowledged that places play a crucial role in shaping and preserving both individual self-identity and the collective identity of a community (Davenport, 2005). Therefore, it can be viewed as a closely intertwined factor in influencing the overall mental and physical well-being of the residents. To be oriented in a space it is essential to have nodes, and landmarks, that are recognizable and easy to remember. Something that is well rooted in the historical memory of the city, something characteristic and unique. The fundamental nature of a location and the significance related to it are strongly influenced by its physical characteristics and conditions (Stedman, 2003), mainly stemming from its environmental traits. The physical features exert influence on the symbolic meanings assigned to the landscape.

In this direction, research developments included the delivery of a questionnaire aimed at identifying the urban landmarks of Piaz-

Fig. 5. Hypothetical border that delimits the city of Piazzola sul Brenta, the result of the interaction between natural and artificial space.

porticoes of Piazza Camerini

Loco delle Vergini

Villa Camerini Contarini

former juty factory

Fig. 6. Paths and landmarks identified in Piazzola sul Brenta.

zola sul Brenta. Since the city is characterized by a rich historical stratification, it was not difficult for participants to identify city landmarks (fig. 5) requested in the questionnaire.

Within the questionnaire proposed to citizens on the historical-cultural value of Piazzola sul Brenta, to the question "When you think of Piazzola sul Brenta which places (individual buildings and/or landscapes) come to mind because they are of particular importance for the community?", the answers were without hesitation and coherent.

The majority chose Villa Contarini Camerini, the park of the Villa, the porticoes of Piazza Paolo Camerini, the square itself, the Brenta's Naturalistic Park, the Brenta river, the jute factory, the Cathedral of the Nativity of Mary and of San Silvestro. Some have also listed the Loco delle Vergini, the Contessa Park, Villa Trieste de Benedetti (included within the municipality of Piazzola sul Brenta).

Conclusions

The recognition of clear and legible landmarks proves the "imageability" of the city of Piazzola and testifies to the readability that these spaces have generated in the collective identity. As the questionnaire shows, historical architectures are landmarks for the citizens of the town.

The ultimate meaning of any building is beyond architecture; it directs our consciousness back to the world and towards our own sense of self and being. Profound architecture makes us experience ourselves as complete embodied and spiritual beings. In fact, this is the great function of all meaningful art. (Pallasmaa, 2005, p. 5)

testifying that Architecture of historical and cultural value is important for the identity of a place and its inhabitants.

The importance of relating buildings to landscape following the visible traces, remains a prerogative for the protection of natural and historic built space. As a result of the questionnaire submitted to citizens, the landmarks identified were not only of an architectural (artificial) nature but also of a natural. This is proof of the connection with the surrounding area, the result of a continuous dialogue over the course of the story. The contemporary necessity to comprehend and represent the knowledge connect to a city and the

Fig 7. Confronting city borders with the river path: on the left the administrative border, in the middle the hypothetical border, on the right the overlapping of the two borders.

interactions between natural and historically built spaces prompts us to integrate both digital and conventional research approaches for future steps, aiming to craft a strategic visualization of these areas (Campi et al., 2022). In this context, several noteworthy studies within the current research domain are worth considering.

One such example is the Visualizing Venice/Visualizing Cities initiative, established in 2010, which examines the art, architecture, and urban history within urban spaces. This initiative emphasizes the significance of how new technologies have the potential to transform research and education by incorporating collaborative theory and practice in the realm of Digital Humanities (Huffman, & Giordano, 2021).

In this particular domain, where space encompasses not only its physical dimensions but also the subjective perceptions of it, adopting an interdisciplinary approach is crucial. Indeed, the methodology for collecting and interpreting data cannot overlook the incorporation of diverse tools. Therefore, the research improves a methodology to interpretate data, supporting an operational verification of the meaning of places, focusing on emotions and meanings that can be used as a strategy for studying not only the territory and the environment, but also the landscape, understood as the result of the perception process (Bianconi et al., 2019).

Fig. 8. Analysing the landscape integrating different tools. The case study of Piazzola sul Brenta.

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